
ISSUES OF APPLICATION OF ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES IN AUDITING

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Annotation. This article examines the importance and practice of applying analytical procedures in the course of audits. Analytical procedures serve as an important tool for auditors to effectively assess financial statements, identify errors and inaccuracies. The article examines the main methods of applying analytical operations, including horizontal and vertical analysis, financial performance analysis, and audit risk management. Also, the role of international auditing standards, in particular ISA 520, in determining how to apply analytical procedures in auditing practice is analyzed. The article highlights the relevance of analytical operations in making the audit process more effective and reducing risks.

Key words. Audit inspections, analytical operations, audit risk, financial analysis, horizontal analysis, vertical analysis, indicator analysis, auditing standards, financial statements, audit strategy, audit efficiency, identification of inaccuracies, risk management, audit processes.

INTRODUCTION. The use of analytical procedures in an audit is important, as it helps to increase the efficiency of the audit process. Analytical procedures are usually used to deeply analyze data and financial statements, identify specific trends, and assess changes in the financial condition or performance of an entity. Analytical procedures during an audit enable auditors to identify relationships between financial information, detect misstatements, and assess risks.

This article provides a detailed analysis of the role and methods of applying analytical procedures in an audit, their role in the audit process, and their contribution to improving its efficiency.

LITERATURE REVIEW. Scientific articles and studies on the use of analytical procedures in audits contain many important aspects. Analytical procedures are an important part of the audit process and help auditors identify material misstatements in financial statements. This article draws attention to the broader work of economists on the use of analytical procedures in auditing practice.

In particular, Gafurov M and Jumanazarov A consider the use of analytical procedures in auditing to be important in increasing the efficiency of the audit process. According to their opinion, “with the help of analytical procedures, auditors can identify changes in financial statements, investigate uncertainties, and draw attention to risky areas. This approach allows for more effective and targeted direction of audit work”.

Professor Tursunov N. also considers the use of analytical procedures in auditing to be an important tool that increases the accuracy and efficiency of the audit process. He notes that “with the help of analytical procedures, auditors can quickly identify inconsistencies in financial statements, assess risks, and, if necessary, conduct a deeper examination, and this method helps auditors to correctly direct audit resources and improve the quality of work”.

Economists Arens and Loebbeck consider analytical procedures to be an important tool in auditing, because through them auditors can identify economic changes and trends in the organization's activities. With the help of analytical procedures, the auditor is able to identify inconsistencies, problem areas, or audit risks in financial statements. According to Arens and Loebbeck, "analytical procedures are of great importance in the timely detection of deviations in reporting and the effective allocation of audit resources".

Another economist, Cohen and Hanno, consider the use of analytical procedures in auditing to be an important tool for making the auditing process more efficient and cost-effective. In their book, "The Practice and Role of Audit Analytical Procedures," they state that with the help of analytical procedures, auditors can quickly identify significant differences in financial statements and clearly direct audit resources to examine them more deeply. This approach helps reduce audit risks and increase accuracy. Knechel and Salterio argue that analytical procedures in auditing are an effective method that helps to increase the accuracy and reliability of the audit. According to them, "analytical procedures help auditors identify significant deviations, find errors or misstatements, and focus on risky areas. This method also allows them to conduct the audit process in a targeted and clear direction".

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. This methodology for studying the application of analytical procedures in auditing consists of the following main stages: 1) Study of theoretical foundations: Determining the essence of analytical procedures and studying how they are used in auditing practice. Determining analytical procedures and their importance in improving audit quality. 2) Data collection and analysis: Collecting data that is in accordance with audit objectives and conducting analysis based on them. Verifying data using statistical methods and analyzing identified errors. 3) Conducting empirical research: Analyzing audit audits in practice. Studying the results of analytical procedures in various enterprises or industries. 4) Analysis of results and drawing conclusions: Assessing the use and effectiveness of analytical procedures in the audit process. Developing recommendations to improve audit quality and reduce errors. Experimental and pilot studies: Conducting practical tests in an audit to study the effectiveness of analytical procedures. Identifying ways to further develop and improve the effectiveness of analytical procedures in audit processes. This research methodology identifies problems related to the effective use of analytical procedures in an audit and develops solutions to them.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. The use of analytical procedures during an audit allows the auditor to more deeply analyze the financial condition of an organization and draw appropriate conclusions. Analytical procedures are an important component of audit activities, which help the auditor assess the reliability of financial statements. These procedures are used to achieve a number of goals, in particular, to identify risks, find unreasonable or incorrect indicators, as well as to improve the efficiency of processes.

Purpose of applying analytical procedures: Analytical procedures are used by auditors during the audit to understand the financial condition of the audited entity, identify anomalies and indicate possible errors in the financial statements. This method is used in the initial stages of the audit, as well as in final audits.

Advantages:

1. **Quick assessment:** Analytical procedures provide quick results through calculations and comparisons. This helps auditors quickly assess the accuracy of the data.
2. **Cost savings:** These procedures save a lot of time and costs during the audit process, as they reduce the need for extensive inspections.
3. **Extensive coverage:** Analytical procedures allow for a more in-depth analysis by identifying relationships between financial indicators and statements.

Disadvantages:

Level of accuracy: Analytical procedures only help identify common errors. They do not always allow for decisions to be made based on specific facts.

Subjectivity: Auditors may make subjective judgments about the results of analytical procedures, which can lead to incorrect decisions.

Steps in applying analytical procedures:

1. Preliminary analysis: Auditors compare various financial indicators with previous periods to identify trends. This stage usually includes growth rates, profitability, and liquidity.

2. Comparative analysis: Auditors compare the company's key indicators with other organizations or industry averages. This process helps identify uncertainties and assess the reasonableness of financial information.

3. Horizontal and vertical analysis: Horizontal analysis shows the dynamics of changes by comparing several periods, while vertical analysis involves analyzing the share of a part of the financial statement in relation to the total. This allows auditors to identify changes in processes.

4. Forecasting and variance analysis: Financial statements are compared with forecasted results or budgets. Through these procedures, auditors analyze differences between budget and actual indicators and determine the reasons for them.

Advantages of using analytical procedures:

- Identifying errors and increasing the reliability of financial statements.
- Identifying risks and correctly directing audit processes.
- Accurate and effective analysis of the financial position.

The table below presents a horizontal analysis of the balance sheet of JSC "Kiziltepa Flour Mill" (Table 1).

Table 1

Horizontal analysis of the balance sheet of JSC “Kiziltepa Flour Mill”

(mln. sums)

Balance sheet asset	At the beginning of the reporting period	By the end of the reporting period	Difference +,-	Growth, %
1	2	3	4(3-2)	5(3/2)*100-100
Asset				
Long-term assets	5450189.00	4320867.00	-1129322	-20.72
Current assets	56033713.00	41587763.00	-14445950	-25.78
Total assets	61483902.00	45908630.00	-15575272	-25.33
Passive				
Source of own funds	5029679.00	5055425.00	25746	0.51
Liabilities	56454223.00	40853205.00	-15601018	-27.64
Total liabilities	61483902.00	45908630.00	-15575272	-25.33

In the horizontal analysis of the balance sheet of JSC "Kiziltepa Flour Mill", the difference in long-term assets at the end of the reporting period compared to the beginning of the reporting period was -1129322 soums, and the growth rate was -20.72%. Current assets at the end of the

reporting period amounted to -14445950 soums, and the growth rate was -25.78%. Total assets at the end of the reporting period amounted to -15575272 soums, and the growth rate was -25.33%.

Now, moving on to the passive part, the difference in the source of the enterprise's own funds at the end of the reporting period compared to the beginning of the reporting period was 25746 soums, liabilities were -15601018 soums, and total liabilities were -15575272 soums. Now, if we look at the growth figures, the source of own funds was +0.51%, liabilities -27.64%, and total liabilities -25.33%.

According to the conclusion of this table, the data presented in the horizontal analysis of the balance sheet of JSC "Kiziltepa Flour Plant" show that all indicators decreased compared to the beginning of the year, except for the indicator of the source of own funds on the passive side, which increased by half a percent.

CONCLUSION. The use of analytical procedures in audit audits is of great importance for the effective organization of the audit process and assessment of the reliability of financial statements. With the help of these procedures, auditors quickly and accurately identify the relationships between financial indicators and reveal significant inconsistencies in the reports. At the same time, analytical procedures allow for a thorough analysis of the development and stability of the activities of the audited organization. Based on the conditions of modernization of the economy, the following conclusions were drawn on the development of auditing activities in Uzbekistan, in particular, on improving the quality of audit audits and methods for obtaining audit evidence. It is necessary to legally develop and materially support the organization of work in this area. Attract international specialists and provide modern literature for the training and retraining of accountants and auditors. Organize the teaching staff of our country to develop our own auditing industry.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that our Republic is establishing equal, reliable and long-term cooperative relations with the world's leading and economically developed countries at the international level. Therefore, it is necessary to further improve the development of national accounting and auditing standards and their implementation in accordance with the practice of our Republic and the requirements of international accounting and auditing standards.

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